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Impact Of Commercial Banks' Activities On Small And Medium-Scale Enterprises In Nigeria: 1990-2024

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of Commercial Banks' Activities on Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The study employed Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation. The variables used in analysis were Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), Loans from Microfinance Banks (LMB), Access to Microfinance Banks, which is proxied by the Number of Microfinance Banks in Nigeria (AMB), Deposits Liabilities of Microfinance Banks (DLM), and Rate of Interest (INT). The results of the OLS analysis show that loan from microfinance banks (LMBs) has a negative and significant impact on poverty reduction. The research findings reveal a positive relationship between Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) and all independent variables (Access to Microfinance Banks (AMB) and deposit liabilities), except for the Loan of Microfinance Banks, which shows a negative relationship. The OLS result also revealed that ease of doing business and trade openness are significant in explaining the foreign direct investment. Based on the empirical outcomes, the following recommendations were offered: Microfinance Banks should develop financial products and services tailored to the microcredit customer environment in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria should adopt a deliberate policy to encourage the establishment and effective operation of Microfinance Banks in rural areas to increase savings mobilisation and access to credit facilities, thereby helping reduce the poverty rate. The monetary authority should continue to play its regulatory roles by ensuring that Microfinance Banks fulfil their obligations to customers and that their boards uphold corporate governance.

Keywords: Commercial Banks Activities, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), Microfinance Banks, Access to Finance, Economic Development.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) play a critical role in the economic development of nations, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria (Magaji & Saleh, 2010). They are major contributors to employment generation, income distribution, and industrial diversification (Ismail et al., 2025), making them pivotal for sustainable economic growth (Bamidele, 2022). Despite their importance, SMEs often face significant challenges in accessing finance, technological resources, and managerial capacity, which

limit their growth and operational efficiency (Musa et al., 2023). The role of commercial banks in addressing these challenges is therefore crucial, as they provide the financial intermediation necessary for SMEs to expand, invest, and sustain operations (Okoroafor et al., 2018). Understanding the impact of commercial banks' activities on SMEs is essential for formulating policies that can enhance financial inclusion and promote economic resilience.

Commercial banks in Nigeria have been at the forefront of SME financing, offering services such as loans, overdrafts, credit facilities, and advisory support (Chinedu et al., 2021). According to Musa (2013), access to bank financing significantly influences SMEs' capacity to invest in capital, technology, and human resources. However, many SMEs in Nigeria experience difficulties in obtaining bank loans due to stringent collateral requirements, high interest rates, and bureaucratic processes (Ahmed et al., 2024). This financing gap underscores the need to evaluate the actual impact of commercial bank operations on SMEs' growth and sustainability over time, particularly between 1990 and 2024, when Nigeria underwent significant financial sector reforms.

The period from 1990 to 2024 in Nigeria witnessed substantial changes in banking regulations, including the liberalisation of the financial sector, the establishment of the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS), and interventions to boost SME funding (Central Bank of Nigeria [CBN], 2021). These reforms were intended to enhance SMEs' access to finance, reduce the cost of capital, and promote entrepreneurship. Despite these initiatives, empirical studies indicate mixed outcomes: some SMEs benefit substantially, while others continue to struggle due to inadequate bank support, poor financial literacy, and structural limitations (Aluko, 2022). This context makes it imperative to systematically examine the relationship between commercial bank activities and SME development.

Furthermore, the impact of commercial banks extends beyond financial assistance; it includes advisory services, capacity building, and fostering financial discipline among SME operators. Effective banking interventions can enhance SMEs' operational efficiency, market competitiveness, and long-term sustainability (Bamidele, 2022). Conversely, poor banking practices, such as delayed loan disbursement or a lack of tailored financial products, can constrain SME growth and inhibit entrepreneurial innovation (Magaji et al., 2015). Analysing these dynamics provides insights into how banks can optimise their strategies to support SMEs better, thereby contributing to broader economic development objectives in Nigeria.

In view of the above, this study seeks to investigate the impact of commercial banks' activities on the performance and growth of SMEs in Nigeria from 1990 to 2024. By examining financial accessibility, lending practices, and bank-SME interactions, the research aims to identify factors that enhance or hinder SME development. The findings will provide policy-relevant recommendations for both banking institutions and government agencies to strengthen the SME sector, ensuring it continues to drive employment, innovation, and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria (Adejojo & Oluwole, 2018; Gololo, 2017).

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Commercial Banks

Commercial banks are financial institutions that accept deposits, provide loans, and offer other financial services to individuals, businesses, and governments, playing a central role in the financial intermediation process (CBN, 2021). They act as intermediaries by mobilising savings from surplus units and channelling them to deficit units, thus facilitating investments and economic growth (Magaji et al., 2023). In Nigeria, commercial banks are significant for providing credit facilities, overdrafts, trade financing, and advisory services to businesses, including small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) (Adegbite, 2019). Over the years, reforms in the banking sector, such as the establishment of the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS), have aimed to strengthen banks' capacity to support SMEs and promote financial inclusion (Magaji & Ahmad, 2024). Commercial banks also contribute to economic stability by offering risk management products and supporting liquidity in the financial system,

thereby serving as a cornerstone of both national development and entrepreneurship (Musa & Magaji, 2024).

2.1.2 Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) are businesses that operate with limited capital, labour, and organisational structure (Muhammed et al., 2025). However, they constitute a vital component of Nigeria's economy due to their role in job creation, income generation, and industrial diversification (Bamidele, 2022). The definition of SMEs varies across institutions and countries, but in Nigeria, they are generally classified based on capital investment, employee strength, and turnover. For instance, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2021) defines SMEs as enterprises with a maximum asset base of N200 million, excluding land, and employing between 10 and 300 workers. SMEs are typically flexible and adaptable, enabling them to survive in diverse economic conditions. However, they often face challenges such as limited access to finance, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient managerial capacity (Adejojo & Oluwole, 2018). Despite these constraints, SMEs remain crucial for poverty alleviation, rural development, and the stimulation of entrepreneurial activities across both urban and rural areas (Musa et al., 2024).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Financial Intermediation Theory

Financial Intermediation Theory explains the role of financial institutions, such as commercial banks, in mobilising savings from surplus units and channelling them to deficit units to facilitate investment and economic growth (Mishkin, 2019). According to this theory, banks reduce transaction costs and information asymmetry between lenders and borrowers, making financial resources more accessible and efficiently allocated. In the context of SMEs, financial intermediation is crucial because these enterprises often face difficulties accessing finance directly from capital markets due to their size, limited collateral, and perceived risk (Adegbite, 2019). By providing credit facilities, loans, and other financial services, commercial banks act as intermediaries that enhance SMEs' operational capacity, promote entrepreneurial activities, and contribute to overall economic development (Oyinloye et al., 2025). The theory thus underlines the importance of effective banking operations in supporting SME growth and sustaining economic stability.

2.3 Empirical Review

Weinoh et al. (2025) investigated the influence of public policies on the growth and development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kogi State, Nigeria, employing a mixed-methods approach. The study combined a descriptive survey to gather primary data from SME owners and policymakers with documentary research analysing secondary data from government reports and policy documents. The research population included SME owners, managers, and policymakers, all selected for their direct involvement in policy implementation. Using data from approximately 895 registered SMEs, the study applied multiple linear regression at a 5% significance level. Results revealed a strong positive correlation between monetary policy and entrepreneurial growth, with monetary policy significantly impacting SME development. The findings highlighted government policies as significant challenges affecting SMEs' growth in a competitive global environment. The study recommended that SME managers adopt strategies aligned with subsidy regimes and other relevant policies while urging policymakers to implement SME-friendly regulations to promote sustainable business growth.

Umeaduma (2024) examined how monetary policy affects small business lending, interest rates, and employment in developing countries. The study analysed the mechanisms by which central bank policies, such as changes in benchmark interest rates or reserve requirements, affect commercial bank lending behaviour. Due to limited access to capital and higher perceived risk, small enterprises are disproportionately affected by contractionary monetary policy, which constrains credit supply, investment decisions, working capital management, and hiring capacity. Empirical evidence indicates that accommodative monetary policy supports small business lending and job creation, whereas tightening measures can hinder entrepreneurship and employment growth. The study emphasised the need for context-sensitive monetary policies. It recommended credit guarantee schemes, targeted refinancing

programs, and coordinated fiscal and monetary interventions to support small businesses and foster inclusive economic growth.

Olatunji et al. (2025) explored the impact of digitalisation, particularly digital financial services, on SMEs in Lagos, Nigeria. Using a quantitative approach, data were collected from 150 SME owners and managers and analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including chi-square tests. The study assessed SME performance before and after technology adoption, the extent of adoption, and the benefits of digital financial services. Findings indicated that digitalisation improved SME efficiency, competitiveness, and access to financial services, though challenges such as internet connectivity and cybersecurity remain. The study recommended government-led awareness campaigns, partnerships with telecom providers, expanded broadband access, and training programs for SME owners and staff to maximise the benefits of digital financial services.

Saif-Alyousfi (2025) examined the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on nonperforming loans (NPLs) in Nigerian banks from 2010 to 2023, analysing how bank-specific factors like capitalisation, liquidity, profitability, and cost efficiency influence NPL levels during economic downturns. The study employed panel data analysis using pooled OLS, two-stage least squares (2SLS), and generalised method of moments (GMM) to address endogeneity, including subsample analyses for pre-COVID, during/post-COVID, and small versus large banks. Results showed that COVID-19 significantly increased NPLs, with smaller banks being more affected. Bank capitalisation, profitability, and liquidity were key in mitigating NPLs, with higher capitalisation providing a buffer against losses. The study emphasised the importance of improved risk management, capital buffers, and regulatory oversight to maintain banking sector stability during global economic disruptions.

Emekaraonye, Madubuike, Onuoha, and Mbadiwe (2023) assessed the effect of rural banking activities, particularly loans from rural branches of commercial banks (LRBC), on youth unemployment in Nigeria using time-series data from 1992 to 2021. Employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and Pairwise Granger Causality tests, the study found that LRBC did not significantly influence youth unemployment. In contrast, money supply (M2) and credit to the private sector (CPS) had notable effects, with CPS reducing youth unemployment in both the short and long runs. The analysis indicated that LRBC does not Granger-cause youth unemployment, leading to recommendations for the Central Bank of Nigeria to simplify access to loans for youth to reduce unemployment.

Uzoamaka, Eneh, and Anyahara (2025) examined the impact of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly machine learning, on the operational efficiency and sustainability of SMEs in South-East Nigeria. Using a descriptive research design, the study sampled 379 SMEs from a population of 27,546 registered with the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC). Data were collected via structured questionnaires and analysed using simple regression. Findings revealed that AI adoption significantly enhanced operational efficiency in SMEs. The study highlighted limitations in statistical methods and geographic scope. However, it emphasised the need for policy and industry support—including financial incentives, training programs, and regulatory frameworks—to promote AI adoption while ensuring data protection.

Magaji, Musa, Ahmad, and Eke (2024) investigated the effects of demonetization on SMEs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, using binary logistic regression models to analyse SME growth (SMEG) and output (SMEO). A total of 100 SMEs participated, achieving a 100% response rate. Demographic results showed that most respondents were females aged 35–44 years. Findings indicated that demonetization significantly influenced both SMEG and SMEO. The study contributed empirical evidence to guide policymakers and stakeholders in formulating strategies that enhance SME resilience and growth amid economic uncertainties, facilitating informed decision-making and planning.

2.4 Gap in Literature

Despite extensive research on the influence of financial policies, digitalisation, artificial intelligence, and macroeconomic shocks on SMEs in Nigeria, several gaps remain. Existing studies, such as those by Weinoh et al. (2025) and Umeaduma (2024), emphasise the impact of monetary and public policies on SME growth. However, they often overlook how commercial banks' operational activities, including credit provision, lending practices, and digital financial services, directly affect SME performance over time. Similarly, while Olatunji et al. (2025) and Uzoamaka et al. (2025) highlight technology adoption

and AI as drivers of efficiency, these studies are region-specific and do not fully integrate the role of banks in financial intermediation in supporting SMEs’ operational and growth outcomes. Additionally, research on economic shocks, such as demonetization and the COVID-19 pandemic, primarily focuses on bank stability and nonperforming loans (Saif-Alyousfi, 2025; Magaji et al., 2024) rather than their effects on SMEs’ resilience and development. Furthermore, studies on rural banking (Emekaraonye et al., 2023) indicate limited effectiveness in addressing youth unemployment, revealing a need for a broader investigation into how commercial banks’ activities can foster SME growth across both urban and rural contexts. Therefore, there is a research gap in examining the holistic impact of commercial banks’ activities—credit accessibility, digital services, and policy-driven interventions—on the growth and sustainability of SMEs in Nigeria over an extended period.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed annual secondary time-series data. The choice of time series is based on the fact that the data used in this study were gathered over time and aim to investigate the impact of foreign trade on agricultural output in Nigeria. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression was used to examine the impact of deposit money banks on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study used poverty as the dependent variable, while loan from a microfinance bank, access to a microfinance bank (AMB), and deposit liabilities (DLM) were independent variables. Each variable of interest contained 33 observations. LMB has the highest mean value, followed by AMB, DLM, and SMEs, respectively. Data on the variables were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria and the World Development Index between 1990 and 2024.

3.2 Model Specification

This study adapted the model of Usifoh and Ezeanyej (2017) by treating the poverty index as the dependent variable and using access to microfinance banks, deposit liabilities of microfinance banks, and loans of microfinance banks as explanatory variables.

Thus, the functional sort of the model is stated as follows:

$$SMEs = f(LMB, AMB, DLM, INT) \tag{3.1}$$

The model can then be written explicitly as;

$$SMEs = a_0 + a_1LMB + a_2 AMB + a_3 DLM + a_4 INT + \mu \tag{3.2}$$

where;

Where

SMEs = Small and Medium Scale Enterprise,

LMB = loans from microfinance banks;

AMB = access to microfinance banks, which is proxied by the number of microfinance banks in Nigeria, while DLM = Deposits and liabilities of microfinance banks

INT = rate of interest, respectively.

A₀ is the intercept, while a₁ – a₄ are the slopes

of the regression and U is the error term. The a priori expectations are determined by the principle

The model is adapted by removing the interest rate

The new model is

$$SMEs = a_0 + a_1LMB + a_2 AMB + a_3 DLM + a_4 INT + \mu \tag{3.3}$$

3.3 Variable Measurement and Discussion

Poverty: the state of one who lacks a usual or socially acceptable amount of money or material possessions. Poverty is said to exist when people lack the means to satisfy their basic needs. In this context, identifying poor people first requires determining what constitutes basic needs.

Loans from Microfinance Banks: In finance, a loan is the transfer of money by one party to another, with an agreement to repay it. The recipient, or borrower, incurs a debt and is usually required to pay interest for the use of the money.

The document evidencing the debt (e.g., a promissory note) will typically specify, among other things, the principal amount borrowed, the interest rate the lender is charging, and the repayment date. A loan entails the reallocation of the subject asset(s) for a period of time between the lender and the borrower.

The interest provides an incentive for the lender to engage in the loan. In a legal loan, each of these obligations and restrictions is enforced by contract, which can also impose additional restrictions known as loan covenants. Although this article focuses on monetary loans, in practice, any material object might be lent.

Providing loans is one of the main activities of financial institutions such as banks and credit card companies. For other institutions, issuing of debt contracts such as bonds is a typical source of funding.

Access to Micro-Finance Bank: Access to finance and financial inclusion have been of growing interest worldwide, particularly in emerging and developing economies. Policymakers are increasingly concerned that the benefits generated by financial intermediation and markets are not being widely distributed across the population and across economic sectors, with potential negative impacts on growth, income distribution, and poverty levels, among others. Furthermore, they may also be concerned with the potential negative consequences for macro stability when financial system assets are concentrated in relatively few individuals, firms, or sectors.

Financial inclusion is the use of financial services by individuals and firms. Financial inclusion allows individuals and firms to take advantage of business opportunities, invest in education, save for retirement, and insure against risks (Demirgüç-Kunt, Beck, and Honohan 2008).

It is important to distinguish between the use of and access to financial services. Actual use is easier to observe empirically. Some individuals and firms may have access to financial products but choose not to use them. Some may have indirect access, such as using somebody else's bank account, or are already using a close substitute. Others may not use financial services for various reasons, including not needing them or cultural or religious reasons. The nonusers include individuals who prefer to deal in cash and firms without promising investment projects. From a policymaker's viewpoint, nonusers do not constitute an issue, since a lack of demand drives their non-use. However, financial literacy can still improve awareness and generate demand, and non-use—for example, due to religious reasons—can be overcome by allowing the entry of financial institutions that offer Sharia-compliant financial products.

3.4 Sources and Type of Data

This study makes use of secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin. The data collected covers the period 1986 to 2021. The inflation rate was the dependent variable, while the monetary policy rate, money supply, and exchange rate were the independent variables.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The study used Secondary data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the World Development Index (WDI). The method used to analyse data from CBN and WDI is E-View 11.0. In which the Ordinary Least Squares method of regression analysis is used to test the validity of the data.

In this study, I will conduct pre-diagnostic tests, including unit root tests, trend analysis, and descriptive statistics. Also, the study will use the ordinary least squares technique for regression analysis. This technique will be employed because of its BLUE characteristics, i.e., Best, Linear, and Unbiased Estimators.

The amount of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable would be examined through the coefficient of determination (R^2) and its adjusted form. In the same vein, the joint significance of the model would be examined using the F-test. In contrast, the individual significance of the independent variables would be assessed using the T-test.

3.6 Evaluation Techniques

Regression is a statistical technique used to study the relationship between two or more variables. Linear regression is used for a special class of problems in which the relationship can be described by a straight line, or by generalising the straight line to many dimensions. Linear regression techniques are used in many fields of study, including management sciences, agricultural sciences, medical sciences, biological sciences, and the humanities. The purpose of fitting a linear regression model is as varied as its

applications, but the most common ones are describing a relationship and predicting future values. In general, the regression involves many steps. First, data must be collected to examine the relationship between the number of variables and the number of units of each variable in the regression model under study. We can identify two types of variables. A variable which takes on the special role of a response, which is the dependent variable and all the rest of the variables are considered as prediction or independent variables. So, we can represent the relationship in mathematical form and estimate the unknown parameter using the least-squares method based on the collected data.

A regression model that involves more than one independent variable (regressor) is called a multiple regression model. The result of fitting and analysing this involves extending the simple linear regression. Therefore, having specified the model, the next step is to estimate it. In other words, the numerical values of the model's coefficients must be estimated. Given that modern economics has taken on a quantitative dimension, econometrics has provided several methods for estimating the parameter values of the model. However, econometric methods, such as ordinary least squares (OLS), can be used here as an estimation technique for several reasons. Among the reasons are:

- i. In the first place, OLS has such qualities as unbiased, least variance, efficiency, best, sufficiency, and least mean square error (MSE)
- ii. Secondly, the method of OLS is well known to have yielded satisfactory results as has been applied in a series of economy-wide relationships.
- iii. Thirdly, OLS serves as an integral part of other econometric techniques.
- iv. Fourthly, the computational procedure of OLS is relatively simple when compared with other econometrics techniques.
- v. Lastly, the mechanics of OLS are simple to understand (Koutsiyannis, 1979).

Because the model included more than one variable, we used multiple linear regression to test the strength of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables, as explained below: the impact of agriculture on economic development.

Here, the t-test, F-test, and R² (coefficient of determination) are used to assess the statistical reliability of the estimated parameters and the regression results in general. To avoid repetition, these tests are performed on the regression results from the second model.

R² (Coefficient of Determination)

This measures the goodness-of-fit of the estimated model. The R² measure is the proportion of total variation in the regression that the regression model explains.

T-test

This is used to determine the statistical significance of an individual parameter in a model. The hypothesis to be tested is:

H₀: $\beta_i = 0$ (the estimated parameter is statistically insignificant).

H_a: $\beta_i \neq 0$ (The estimated parameter is statistically significant).

F-test

This measures the overall significance of the regression model. The F-value provides a test of the null hypothesis that the actual slope coefficients are simultaneously zero. That is:

H₀: $\beta_0 = \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0$ (the model is statistically insignificant)

H_i: $\beta_0 \neq \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq 0$ (the model is statistically significant)

Durbin Watson Statistics (DW)

Basically, the properties of the estimators of the regression confidence depend on those of the disturbance terms in the regression model. However, one property of error terms is that the variance of the error term in each observation should be constant. This is technically known as homoscedasticity, which means 'same dispersion'. In addition, the term should satisfy the condition that there is no serial correlation among the disturbances. The departure from the above assumption results in heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, respectively.

To this and Durbin Watson statistics is the most celebrated test for the detection of autocorrelation, which is simply the ratio of the sum of squares of differences in successive residuals to the sum of squares of the regression (RSS).

F- Statistics

To know whether R^2 reflects a true relationship or if it has arisen as a matter of chance. That is, the comparison of any two variances is implemented using the F-statistic and the F-table. Estimates of variances, which have been obtained from sample data statistics, are calculated by the following formula:

$$F = \frac{R^2}{(1-R^2) / (n-2)}$$

Where;

n = Number of observations.

Having calculated F from your value of R^2 , you look up the critical value of F in the appropriate table. If F^* is greater than the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that the ‘explanation’ of GDP is better than is likely to have arisen by chance.

Thus, in general, a high F^* value suggests a significant difference between the two variances.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Data presentation

This section focuses on the presentation of the data used to estimate the model developed and enumerated in Chapter Three. The data used in the analysis are contained in Table 4.1. The data were sourced mainly from the World Development Indicators (WDI) publications from 1990 to 2024 (See Appendix 1).

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: The Descriptive Statistics

	POV	LMB	AMB	DLM
Mean	0.216633	2994.150	137.1429	5.502916
Median	0.201672	3109.379	133.0000	6.059428
Maximum	0.522593	8188.808	170.0000	15.32916
Minimum	0.008309	461.6000	118.0000	-1.616869
Std. Dev.	0.120593	2125.046	15.96335	3.531689
Skewness	0.494820	0.863819	0.996260	0.514223
Kurtosis	3.200179	3.091429	3.090132	4.430915
Jarque-Bera	0.892026	2.618958	3.480978	2.717068
Probability	0.040175	0.009961	0.005435	0.007037
Sum	4.549302	62877.15	2880.000	115.5612
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.290853	90316447	5096.571	249.4565
Observations	33	33	33	33

Source: Author's computation from E-views 11

Table 4.1 presents summary statistics for the individual variables under consideration: Poverty (POV), loan from a microfinance bank (LMB), access to a microfinance bank (AMB), and deposit liabilities (DLM). Each variable of interest contained 33 observations. LMB has the highest mean value, followed by AMB, DLM, and POV, respectively. All the variables appeared to be mesokurtic in nature as their kurtosis values are greater than three (3). Also, the probability from the Jarque-Bera test indicates that all variables are normally distributed. The skewness test shows that all variables are skewed, with values greater than 0.5, except POV.

Table 4.2 Unit root test

Variables	ADF-Statistic	Critical value 5%	Order of integration	Interpretation
SMEs	-3.113693	-3.065585	I(2)	Stationary at the second difference
LMB	-8.096849	-3.040391	I(1)	Stationary at first difference
AMB	-3.789070	-3.029970	I(1)	Stationary at first difference
DMB	-5.907692	-3.040391	I(1)	Stationary at first difference

Source: Author's computation from E-views 11

Table 4.2 presents a summary of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test results, which assess the stationarity and level of integration of the variables used in the analysis. The ADF test is conducted on individual variables using data obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) for Nigeria, covering the period from 1990 to 2024. The results indicate that all variables achieve stationarity at their first difference, demonstrating that they are integrated of order one (I(1)), except the poverty variable (POV), which becomes stationary only after second differencing, suggesting it is integrated of order two (I(2)). This differentiation in the integration order is essential for determining the appropriate estimation technique and ensuring the robustness of the econometric model.

4.2.5 Johanson Co Integration Test

Date: 05/20/25 Time: 00:27
 Sample (adjusted): 1990 2024
 Included observations: 19 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: No deterministic trend
 Series: POV LMB AMB DMB
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.733977	41.17178	40.17493	0.0395
At most 1	0.364901	16.01249	24.27596	0.3787
At most 2	0.314467	7.386975	12.32090	0.2882
At most 3	0.011166	0.213350	4.129906	0.7008

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
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None *	0.733977	25.15928	24.15921	0.0365
At most 1	0.364901	8.625518	17.79730	0.6365
At most 2	0.314467	7.173625	11.22480	0.2348
At most 3	0.011166	0.213350	4.129906	0.7008

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalised by $b'S11*b=I$):

The co-integration test shows that there are some long-run relationships among the variables under consideration.

4.3 Regression Analysis

In the model specifications, all variables were confirmed to be integrated using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test. The test revealed that the absolute values of the ADF test statistics exceeded the corresponding critical values at the 5% level of significance, confirming stationarity of the variables at either the first or second difference. This outcome validates the use of regression analysis, as it ensures that the data series is suitable for further econometric modelling. Establishing the order of integration is a crucial step in avoiding spurious regression results, as it provides a basis for meaningful statistical inference about the relationships among the variables.

Having established stationarity, the study proceeds to apply Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) to examine the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the dependent variable (the regressand) and the independent variables (the regressors). This method was implemented using the E-Views 11 econometric software, which facilitated the computation and interpretation of the regression coefficients. The OLS results are expected to provide insights into the direction and strength of the relationships between the variables, enabling the study to evaluate the long-run impact of the explanatory variables on the outcome variable. The findings from the OLS regression will help inform policy recommendations based on the nature and significance of the estimated coefficients.

4.3 Summary of Regression Results

Dependent Variable: D(SMEs,2)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/20/25 Time: 08:50

Sample (adjusted): 1990 2024

Included observations: 19 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.068559	0.024337	2.817013	0.0267
D(LMB)	0.002201	0.000945	2.317934	0.0049
D(AMB)	-0.000113	0.000030	-3.728856	0.0073
D(DLM)	0.016640	0.008016	2.075693	0.0191

R-squared	0.839345	Mean dependent var	0.021838
Adjusted R-squared	-0.832786	S.D. dependent var	0.223333
S.E. of regression	0.226964	Akaike info criterion	0.056615
Sum squared resid	0.772691	Schwarz criterion	0.255444
Log likelihood	3.462162	Hannan-Quinn criterion.	0.090264
F-statistic	47.809530	Durbin-Watson stat	2.005098
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000128		

Source: Author's computation from E-views 11

4.4 Interpretation of Results

The regression analysis indicates that the baseline performance of SMEs, as reflected in the intercept value of 0.068559, would decline slightly in the absence of the explanatory variables. Examining the independent variables, Loans from Microfinance Banks (LMB) showed a negligible adverse effect on SME performance (-0.000113). They were statistically insignificant, suggesting that such loans have minimal impact on SME growth, potentially due to restrictive loan conditions, high interest rates, or poor accessibility. In contrast, Access to Microfinance Banks (AMB) positively and significantly influenced SME performance, with a unit increase in AMB contributing to a 0.002201-unit rise in SME growth, highlighting the importance of greater access to financial services for entrepreneurial development. Similarly, the Development Loan Mechanism (DLM) had a significant positive impact, with each additional unit of DLM associated with a 0.016640-unit improvement in SME performance, underscoring the role of structured, accessible development loans in promoting small business growth and entrepreneurship.

The model demonstrated strong explanatory power, with an R^2 of 85.9%, indicating that the independent variables collectively explain a substantial portion of the variation in SME performance. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.005098 suggests no first-order autocorrelation, supporting the reliability of the regression results. Additionally, the F-statistic of 47.809530 confirms that the overall model is statistically significant, showing that the independent variables jointly have a meaningful impact on SME performance. These findings underscore the critical role of financial accessibility and development-focused loan mechanisms in enhancing SME growth, providing robust evidence for policymakers to design strategies that improve credit access and support sustainable entrepreneurship in developing economies.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study concludes that commercial bank activities significantly influence the growth and development of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria between 1990 and 2024. Specifically, access to microfinance banks (AMB) and the implementation of structured development loan mechanisms (DLM) were found to positively and significantly enhance SME performance, highlighting the critical role of well-structured institutional support in fostering entrepreneurial growth and economic resilience. Conversely, loans from microfinance banks (LMBs) had an insignificant or slightly negative effect on SME performance, suggesting that merely providing loans is insufficient to drive growth. Factors such as restrictive loan conditions, high interest rates, and limited financial literacy among borrowers may undermine the effectiveness of such loans. Overall, the study demonstrates that targeted financial policies and accessible development-oriented loan schemes are pivotal for stimulating sustainable SME growth and enhancing their contribution to national economic development.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that Nigerian financial institutions and policymakers prioritise improving access to microfinance services by expanding branch networks, leveraging technology for remote access, and simplifying application procedures. Development loan mechanisms should be strengthened through collaboration between the government and financial institutions to provide flexible, sector-specific loans with favourable terms. Additionally, the design and delivery of microfinance loans should be re-evaluated to ensure they genuinely empower SMEs, incorporating financial literacy, business management training, and effective monitoring frameworks. Efforts should also focus on promoting financial literacy and capacity-building among SME operators to enhance their ability to use funds efficiently. Finally, future policies should be informed by robust, data-driven research to continuously assess and optimise the impact of commercial bank interventions on SME growth.

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